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What are the Key Elements of Classroom Practice that Meet the Super-Diverse Personalised Demands of Adult Learners in VET?

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Abstract

Context: Adult educational practice doesn't adequately promote adult participation in VET in Latvia. One of the obstacles is the discrepancy between the offer provided by VET and the demand adults can accept. This issue is significant from an international perspective.

Approach: The holistic, inclusive approach of this study implies three interconnected sub-systems of universal, selected and indicated personalised needs of VET learners, recognising a range of super-diverse needs of young adults that are not just academic and professional (particularly in dual VET practice).

Findings: The findings of the study reveal the "resistance theorists' perspective": students react to the form rather than the substance of schooling. This is evident in young adults' narratives, which appeal for changes in schooling organisation, discover the key elements of the process of schooling and its crucial didactic design elements, guiding the learning classes towards understanding subject-matter content in a way that helps the students to think and participate in productive dialogue with teachers, encouraging young adults to embed the acquired school-matter-knowledge in their own work and life.

Conclusion: The key elements of classroom practice that meet the super-diverse personalised demands of adult learners in VET may affect their attitudes toward learning and, in turn, their learning behaviours. All of this means that the analytical results of the current study will be of interest to a wide range of VET stakeholders where the value of adult learning is central.

Keywords: young adults in VET, super-diversity, personalised learning, good classroom practice

1 Introduction

Adult education professionals working in formal VET educational structures with diverse educative patterns and various professional practices should be better equipped to meet the demands expressed by adult learners with fewer opportunities to combine education, training, employment, and family. Adult educators' mission is to contribute to mobilising the potential of these learners by the employment of an alternative cultural schooling perspective in classroom practice, which would enrich all learners faced with many challenges in their personalised social and cultural life and work contexts and better support them all in a world that is increasingly diverse.

Several psychological studies have been conducted in recent years, with Downes (2014) mapping them with a holistic approach that "addresses why people are reluctant to engage in education and training" (p.4) investigated in the context of the need to implement a new holistic structural system of preventive measures. This paper considers these issues, presenting evidence from secondary analyses of low-educated and low-skilled adults' narratives who

frequently struggle to maintain their lives, are disoriented in life and at work, and have low self-esteem.

The secondary analysis of the interviews was conducted in the Asian and European Lifelong Learning (ASEM HUB LLL) perspective in 2011–2015 in the framework of the Latvian National Research Program project "Identification and Analysis of New Challenges and Solutions that Have Influence on Engagement and Reintegration of Adults (18–24 years old) in Lifelong Learning" funded by the ESF project "Support to Education Research" (sub-activity 1.2.2.3.2.), and in 2016–2019 of the interviews of 18–26-year-old young adults) in the Horizon 2020 project "Adult Education as a Means for Active Participatory Citizenship" (EduMAP Grant agreement ID: 693388), in relation to the research question: "What are the key elements of classroom practice that could support adult learning in VET?"

In both investigations (Maslo & Fernández González, 2015; Pata et al., 2021), the "voices" of young adults were analysed in terms of the situation "one is in, why one is in it, and what one can do to get out". We found evidence that a set of complex and multifaceted reasons to reject traditional schooling and we identified the need to implement a targeted preventive strategy and to transform subsequent lifelong learning opportunities.

The paper will discuss the kind of support adult educators need to ensure in order to provide confidence and hope to adult learners who might feel lost, misunderstood, or even abandoned by the VET formal or non-formal education system.

The first chapter will focus on the theoretical definition of super-diversity of personalised learning demand and then discuss the methods to answer the question of how aspirations of low-skilled young adults in Latvia contribute to a successful pathway towards VET education.

The following chapter will describe the key elements of classroom practises that could support adult learning in VET.

Finally, a concluding discussion will be initiated.

2 Super-Diverse Personalised Demands of Adult Learners in VET

The theoretical and methodological approaches to understanding the range of super-diverse needs of young adults that are not just academic and professional and the demands of adult learners in the transformation of schooling in VET are being considered in this paper chapter. Increasingly, literature reviews (e.g. Minns & McFadden, 2000) emphasise that young people have diverse needs. This has enabled a conceptual approach to addressing young people's unmet needs and recognising the diversity in their experiences (e.g. Stokes, 2000), which has made a significant contribution to a holistic, inclusive approach (Dwyer et al., 1998) in transnational perspective and particularly in Latvian education practise (Lieģeniece, 1999).

Based on Burkhart (2004) and Downes's (2014), the holistic, inclusive approach of this study implies interconnected sub-systems of personalised needs of VET learners, recognising a range of super-diverse needs of young adults that are not just academic and professional (particularly in dual VET practise). Those are 1) a universal sub-system for a broad educational community-wide system for all VET learners; 2) a selective sub-system for VET learners at high risk of exclusion from vocational education with a high potential for re-entry to VET; and 3) an indicated specialized, individualised sub-system for adults at high risk of exclusion with chronic multiple risk factors. Following this argument, the multi-faceted nature of the super-diversity of personalised learning needs in this paper is understood as diverse combinations of social well-being (self-confidence, mental health, relationships with teachers and peers in the classroom), and relevance to schooling for learners' life and work in their personal situation.

2.1 Understanding of Adult Learners' Schooling Demands in VET

The understanding of the demands of adult learners in VET (1st objective) was explored using the methodology of "perspective discrepancy assessment" on experienced practice. The

theoretical basis for defining the key elements of classroom practice to support adult learning in VET is built on the "organizational concept of perspective" developed by Mezirow (1981), which consists of three components: 1) a definition of the situation one is in and why one is in it; 2) the conditions that are proper and reasonable to engage in given the situation; and 3) "criteria" of judgement value against which people are judged, developed in the notion of "perspective discrepancy assessment" (p.144-145).

A framework for the case studies for the selection of good practise and for the detailed description of good practice was worked out. This was based on the key factors in determining "good practices" (Federighi & Torlone, 2010, p. 56).

2.2 Methodology for Identifying Key Elements of Classroom Practice to Support Adult Learning in VET

An objective hermeneutic analysis approach (Wernet, 2009), in favour of the youth's 18–26 judgments as the creators of real VET practise and research subjects, was chosen. The researcher was tasked with developing a category system using "open coding" (Corbin & Strauss, 1990), which reveals the conceptual framework of the support adult educators must provide to adult learners who may feel lost, misunderstood, or even abandoned by the VET formal education system (2nd objective).

Two hermeneutic analysis strategies were used for this purpose: empathy and assumption formulation. In the first cycle of hermeneutic analysis, the possibility of software word analysis of the judgments was used to understand the judgement as close as possible to the text (word codes). The second strategy revealed what was meant by the "open coding" judgement in the second cycle of analysis (content codes). In the third cycle of the analysis, a meta-code system was created.

To provide answers to the research questions posed in this paper (3rd objective), "What are the key elements of classroom practise that could support adult learning in VET?", the statements were coded (Saldaña, 2016), particular codes analysed, meta-codes created and added to the texts, a meta-codes analysis table was created and implications determined using AQUAD 7 Qualitative Comparative Analyses (QCA) options (Huber & Gürtler, 2012) to inspect the properties of sufficient and necessary conditions in a data frame, most notably, of minimally sufficient and necessary conditions that appear in cases (Benoît & Ragin, 2008, 63-68; Baumgartner & Thiem, 2015, p. 6).

3 Results

The definition of a range of combinations of super-diverse personalised needs and demands of young adults schooling in VET that is not just academic and professional (1st objective), the conceptual framework of the support adult educators must provide to adult learners who may feel lost, misunderstood, or even abandoned by the VET formal education system (2nd objective), and the key elements of good classroom practise that support adult learning in VET (3rd objective) were defined.

3.1 Super-Diversity of Personalised Needs of Adults

A set of super-diverse combinations of personalised needs that are not just academic and professional has been found in young adults' narratives. The minimally sufficient and necessary universal, selective, and indicated ones that appear in cases are synthesised in the following matrix, see Table1.

Table 1
Matrix: MetaCode: Personalised Needs of Young Adults

Content Codes	Example quotes
Life and work situation (universal)*	<i>I started schooling after 5 years of interruption, because I had an important work ...Then a child came, and I thought that I should start again from the beginning, in order to be able to study choreography (Interview VYA_15). I got pregnant and for two years I did not go to the school. Now I am in 10th grade, my son has 2 years. I study and in parallel I work in a store as seller, I went to some courses (Interview VYA_9).</i>
Limited possibilities of combining schooling with work (selective)**	<i>I also discussed other options, but all the other options stopped when I could combine it with work (Interview VYA_4). ... Of course, I was also very busy at work, so I didn't finish. I don't get along with those long projects. If there was some two-year training or something I do now (Interview VYA_10). If I have to work in parallel, I have not really much time at home for homework. I have many other things to do during the day (Interview VYA_16).</i>
Rejection of traditional schooling (indicated)***	<i>Too many lessons; necessity of going to school for face-to face lessons every day (Interview VYA_15.) Homework overload, where the accent is on homework not on working during the lessons, which does not allow the combination of schooling and hobbies and free time (Interview VYA_29.). Tension on achievement, and therefore giving priority to more successful students rather than promoting the learning success of all (Interview VYA_24).</i>

* Adult learners who return to education and training later in life do so for a variety of subjective and objective reasons, including the birth of a child, army obligations, previous learning experiences, and an unwillingness to learn.

** It is necessary to mention the limited possibilities of combining schooling with work, mainly because there is no school sometimes close to home, due to living in a rural location or by getting a job abroad, not always for earning money, but spurred by the need to feel like an adult or to get work experience.

*** This results in the missed opportunity of success in self-development and the dominance of compulsory learning over voluntary learning, which is based on the individual's desire to learn new things; a lack of opportunities to learn from mistakes, which is a good way to success in learning instead of just counting mistakes in the exams for the purpose of marking (dominantly bad grades); a low social impact of learning outcomes; not getting a better salary; no advancement/promotion in career; and the absence of timely formative feedback on learning quality.

Some similarities permeate all three adults' judgments. These are 1) the value of education as a "criterion" of judgement (value standards by which adult learners have judged their personalised needs); 2) the existence of a transformative learning environment in the family, friends, community, or workplace, and in particular at vocational school (transversal personalised needs).

3.2 Adult Learners' Schooling Demands in VET

A set of super-diverse combinations of personalised demands of adult learners in VET has been found in young adults' narratives, which has to be mentioned in VET. The minimally sufficient and necessary ones that appear in cases are synthesised in the following matrix, see Table 2.

Table 2

Matrix: MetaCode: Adult Learners' Schooling Demands in VET

Content Codes	Example quotes
Organisation of schooling*	<p><i>The Vocational high school was the only one that offered studies in the evening, say in the afternoon around it. Classes started at four until about nine or ten, and then it was possible (Interview VYA_25).</i></p> <p><i>Give more connection with some kind of enterprise so that all that was learned goes somewhere afterwards (Interview VYA_7).</i></p> <p><i>We have actively used e-mail, Skype, face-to-face discussions, and mobile phones. free of charge, available materials and possibilities to use universities' web access to scientific databases, use libraries, use educational materials, I-net, books, collaboration, previous knowledge and practice, scientific web-based portals, participating at web-conference sessions (Interview VYA_2.)</i></p>
Didactical design**	<p><i>The main thing that you learned, and not the fact that you were present in every lecture, and not that all your home tasks are done, is that you know, you understand, and can (Interview VYA_3).</i></p> <p><i>We were from 18 to 29 years old, in case you didn't know, and this is a huge difference. Sitting there on a school bench with their members of the course, this really is a huge difference. Why do we all have to be equated with 18 years old? It just does not work for 25-year-olds. This was a distinct childhood approach... academic and professional education are completely different approaches (Interview VY_30).</i></p> <p><i>I learned that working while studying at the same time has many advantages. Students can implement what they have learned in their practical work. So, they can see how it works and reflect on whether it is a good way to learn, react, or behave for them and how it is for the learners. If it is helpful, you have in mind what you have learned and can try it directly and don't have to be informed again when you want to exercise it later (Interview VYA_5).</i></p>
Process of schooling ***	<p><i>I referred to my real practice, analysed and structured it. The structured critics from my group mates gave me so many useful goals for the future and many ideas for my practise improvement (Interview VYA_23).</i></p> <p><i>I think you can learn every day on the streets. There are people who have never attended school but have learned a lot in their lives by doing their jobs. You feel you have learnt it when you use it in your life (Interview VYA_10).</i></p> <p><i>I learn from my own mistakes and other people's mistakes. The more they do wrong, the more I do right. If I meet a smart person, I feel the need to learn. I feel that I have learnt something when I can say something that I thought was unknown (Interview VYA_21).</i></p>

*Face-to-face, online, or web-based communication is an excellent medium for facilitating social relationships among diverse adult learners. This will help the low-skilled adult learners to maintain their sense of trust or confidence with others since their own point of view is acknowledged in the learning community, developing a sense of collaboration in VET and with enterprises.

** Guiding rather than instructing the learning community toward understanding subject topics in a way that assists adult learners in clarifying their thoughts and participating in a productive work-based dialogue, encouraging them to explore new real and future life and work-related knowledge, creating good relationships with other course participants to enhance their sense of belonging, and positioning themselves critically in the learning community.

*** In particular, a learning environment that facilitates learning only emotionally but not socially is unhelpful – adult VET education must be adult-learner-centred rather than child-centred. Adults need to be able to communicate with the teacher as an equal ‘learning partner’ (learning in dialogue with the teacher as an experienced colleague).

3.3 Important Aspects of Organization of Schooling

The key organisational aspects of support of adult learning that facilitate the engagement of young adults in learning are:

Aspect 1. The learning process has to be organised as a combination of distance learning and blended learning that takes place in different mental, virtual, interpersonal, and physical locations; as motivational, facilitative, and compensatory lessons; and/or as a summary text, presentation of images, or statistical information using interactive learning materials such as videos, demonstrations, etc.

Aspect 2. The organisation of individual, peer and group consultations simultaneously (synchronously) and at different times (asynchronously), using not only e-exercises, e-tasks and e-tests (basic elements of distance learning), but also through collaboration and interaction between adult learners and teachers as adult educators in forum discussions, Skype conferences, chat rooms and surveys (new key elements of an e-learning culture)

Aspect 3. The following opportunities have to be provided for adult learning:

- To learn individually at a pace and time that suits you;
- To combine work and study, for example, by living and working in another country;
- To schedule your own study time;
- To communicate online, as face-to-face attendance is not mandatory;
- Instead of discussing issues with classmates, you should discuss them with people from VET, local communities, and businesses.
- To choose learning resources and learn according to your needs and abilities;
- To acquire new knowledge, develop skills, and demonstrate one's competence in various work and life situations.

3.4 Crucial Didactic Design Elements

Based on the analysis, the implicit key elements for creating cultures of didactic support, oriented to the acquisition of learning outcomes, were unfolded. These key elements indicate the path towards an innovative culture of modernisation of education in a lifelong learning context.

The following key elements of didactic culture were unfolded:

Step1. In this first step, it is important to encourage learners to develop a sense of community:

- To keep the discussion focused on relevant issues that will help the youth learn from the feedback provided about their learning strengths and weaknesses;
- To communicate clearly about the topics and practical tasks of important subject matters;
- To provide clear guidelines instead of instructions on how to participate in learning activities and on the important deadlines for learning activities;
- To identify the topics that facilitate learning among young adults.

Step 2: Guiding the learning community toward understanding subject topics and tasks in a way that assists learners in clarifying their meanings and participating in productive dialogue, encouraging adults to explore new knowledge, build good relationships with other course participants to increase their sense of belonging, and position themselves critically in the learning community, enriching it with their differences.

Step 3. Face-to-face, online or web-based communication is an excellent medium for facilitating social relationships where the adult learners feel socially comfortable. This will help them to maintain their sense of trust or confidence with others since their point of view is acknowledged in the learning community by developing a sense of collaboration.

Step 4. The use of problem-solving activities in the learning process increases the young adults' interest in subject issues, provokes their curiosity, and motivates them to explore content-related questions and use a variety of sources of information for exploring the problems

posed. Brainstorming and finding relevant information help young adult learners solve content-related questions.

Step 5. Face-to-face, online or web-based discussions are valuable in helping young adult learners appreciate different perspectives. Combining new information with previous knowledge will help them to answer practical questions raised during the learning activities more effectively. In this way, their competencies in constructing explanations and solutions and reflecting on subject content will also increase. This will lead to a better understanding of fundamental concepts and will enhance their ability to formulate their own questions and to test and apply in practice the new knowledge they have created.

3.5 Key Elements of the Process of Schooling

The course e-environment has to be designed to support young adults' self-directed independent work by providing broad interactive individual and collaborative e-learning opportunities (via Group-Skype/WhatsApp/ZOOM/Teams, instant messaging, group and joint forums) for active participation in the pedagogically guided course activities of interconnected course sessions/modules.

In self-directed small and peer discussions on work and life situations-oriented inter-disciplinary subject matters topics, the specialised knowledge in specialisation fields for developing new ideas or processes at the forefront of work or study contexts, including research of learners' knowledge, skills, and competences, will be discovered. Active participation in video lectures, live lectures presented on Zoom and recorded prone to dropping out, webinars, and practical virtual activities, directly related to the formulated learning outcomes, will be ensured through effective guiding of young adults' self-directed learning.

The facilitators' staff (teachers, entrepreneurs, etc.) will provide effective pedagogical leadership of individual and collaborative practical activities instead of teaching, ensuring objective and subjective conditions for adult self-directed learning and the achievement of their course's internationally recognised learning outcomes:

3.6 Guidelines for students

Involve yourself in small and peer discussion groups related to session/module units on discovering the specialised knowledge skills in specialisation fields for the development of new ideas or processes at the forefront of work or study contexts, including research of your knowledge, skills, and competences related to learning outcomes assessment questions:

- integrate your informal knowledge of ITC in the studies using Group Skype/WhatsApp/ZOOM/Teams/etc., instant messaging, group-and joint-forums;
- develop and demonstrate your intrapreneurship in collaborative deep studies of the module units' content resources by strengthening the collective capacity of group-mates by creating small and peer-discussion groups for discovering the work or life situation-related issues;
- demonstrate personal involvement in mastering the collaborative activities of small discussion groups and peers;
- demonstrate your participation in the self-improvement of the intended international learning outcomes of peer and small discussion groups;
- demonstrate eagerness and tenacity in transforming project challenges into new learning opportunities;
- giving formative feedback to peers; and making self-assessment of competences using forums and/or self-evaluation-rubrics.

3.7 Guidelines for teachers (trainers/mentors/tutors)

The teacher provides effective pedagogical leadership of collaborative learning versus teaching, ensuring the following objective and subjective conditions for students' successful learning and the achievement of international learning outcomes:

- catalyse the opportunities for integrating students' informal knowledge of ITC into the studies using Group-Skype/WhatsApp/ZOOM/Teams/etc., instant messaging, small groups and joint forums;
 - facilitate the development of students' intrapreneurship in the creation of spiritual, physical, and virtual learning spaces for collaborative deep studies of the topic content resources. strengthening the collective capacity of students for small and peer group discussions on specialised knowledge and skills in specialisation fields for the development of new ideas or processes at the forefront of work or study contexts, including research of their knowledge, skills, and competencies related to learning outcomes assessment questions;
1. support the personal involvement of students in collaborative studies by strengthening learner-to-content interactions in the online learning environment;
 2. provide ongoing and timely formative feedback and competency evaluation;
 3. demonstrate own self-enhancement in facilitating students' success in learning;
 4. facilitate the supportive social climate by strengthening learner-to-instructor and learner-to-learner interactions in the online learning environment.

4 Concluding Discussion

The key elements of classroom practice that support adult learning in VET, referring to the extremely diverse personalised learning needs and learning opportunities demand evident in low-skilled adult narratives, include three essential components.

The implications concern the organisation, didactic and process of facilitating adult learning in general, especially in formal VET, see Figure 1.

Figure 1

Key Elements of Classroom Practice that Meet the Super-Diverse Personalised Demands of Adult Learners in VET

- (1) The demand for the creation of the availability of time for learning in direct connection with life phases and the vocational history of low-skilled adults *as important aspects of the organisation of schooling*;

- (2) The demand for a variety of learning opportunities linked to super-diverse personalised learning needs to be adequately provided by guiding *versus* teaching the learning classes towards understanding subject topics in a way that helps the students to clarify their thinking and participation in productive dialogue encourages adults to explore new A sense of belonging and a sense of trust or confidence since their point of view is acknowledged by others, helps to develop a sense of collaboration that leads to understanding fundamental concepts and the ability to describe the ways to test and apply the created knowledge and develop solutions that have to be applied in practice *as crucial didactic design elements*;
- (3) The demand for productive classroom experience (related to work and daily life, based on less formal and embedded methods, based on codified knowledge which the subject does not yet possess, which is in use in his/her life or work environment) in favour of "learning in dialogue", preferring to learn from experienced, life-wise people, most of whom are teachers, and technological learning frequently affected by social instead of emotional wellbeing *as key elements of the self-directed process of schooling of adults*.

To meet the universal, selective, indicated, and transversal personalised learning needs of adult learners, a complex set of pedagogical measures must be implemented as a holistic system in which vocational education as a value is central in creating a family, school, and workplace community learning culture.

Support cultures of transformational learning opportunities have to be seen as key, as a kind of learning where learning outcomes are reached. In this sense, the positive learning experience of changing the organisation, process and didactic of schooling has an important role.

The results of the secondary analysis of the findings of international studies presented in this paper may contribute to pedagogical knowledge in widely differing fields. The results could also be of interest regarding the theoretical framework and methodology of the presented analysis, with its unique combination of the theories of super-diversity of personalised learning needs of adults at risk of exclusion from education and training, adult learners' demand for inclusive classroom practices, and the evaluation of these, for anyone interested in professional development.

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Biographical notes

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